

Kinematics and Convergent Tectonics of the Northwestern South America plate during the Cenozoic

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Supplemental Material

Table S1. Compilation of the main tectonostratigraphic events in northwestern South America during the Cenozoic.

Figure S1. Three-dimensional view of the tomographic interpretation of the Nazca and Caribbean subducting slabs (GIF animation)

Figure S2. Geometrical evolution of the Farallon, Nazca, Cocos and Caribbean subduction beneath northwestern South America and eastern Central America through the Cenozoic.

Figure S3. Alternative reconstruction of the South and Central American subduction zones considering that the Caribbean slab is subducting east of the Panama-Choco Arc (the preferred reconstruction is found in the main body of the manuscript).

Table S1. Compilation of the main tectonostratigraphic events in northwestern South America during the Cenozoic. Nomenclature at the end.

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
Paleocene	Farallon plate: Aleutyan type subduction-Lateral change between continental and intraoceanic subduction.	Arc	PCA, RC and Southern WC-CC	Farallon arc-related Magmatism during the Paleocene	In Panama: Chagres-Bayano Arc; in northern Colombia: Acandí Batholith, Santa Cecilia La Equis Complex; in southern Colombia: Timbiquí Complex; in Ecuador: Silante and Macuchí arcs	Geoch, ADat.	Cardona et al., 2018; Barbosa-Espitia et al., 2019
			Northern CC, SNSM	Caribbean arc-related Magmatism during the Paleocene. Important crustal thickening around the Antioquia Batholith.	Eastern Antioquia Batholith, Hatillo, Manizales, Norcasia, Bosque, Sonsón and Santa Barbara plutons; Santa Marta Batholith and Parashi Stock	Geoch, ADat.	Bayona et al., 2012; Cardona et al., 2014; Bustamante et al., 2017; Jaramillo et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019
	Caribbean plate: Highly oblique subduction	CC, SNSM and RC	CC, SNSM and RC	First pulse of tectonic exhumation during late Cretaceous-Paleocene time (<1 km/my in the Central Cordillera and >1 km/my in the Real Cordillera)		Strat, prov, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2003; Spikings et al., 2010; Villagómez et al., 2011; Caballero et al., 2013; Mora et al., 2020
			Northern CC	Maximum paleo-elevations in the arc position during the Paleocene		Strat, Thch.	León et al., 2021; Zapata et al., 2021
			Forearc	CV, WC and RC	Paleocene marine fans and turbiditic deposits in the forearc	Penderisco, Nogales, Espinal, Río Piedras, Yunguilla and Santa Elena Fms.	Strat.
	Backarc	CeB, CB	SJR, LMV, TB, southern WC	Regional unconformity in the forearc during the Paleocene		Strat, Prov, Biostr.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2017; Pardo-Trujillo et al., 2020
				Paleocene transition between estuarine-fluvial and shallow marine environments in the CeB and CB	Cuervos Fms.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
			RB, MB	Fault activity since the late Paleocene early Eocene in the RB and northwestern MB		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Kellogg and Vega, 1995; Montes et al., 2010; Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012
			SM	Uplifting episode in the SM during the late Paleocene-Eocene		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012; Siravo et al., 2019
			EC, MV	Transition from shallow marine-marginal to continental deposition in the EC and MV during the Paleocene	Lisama, Hoyon, La Seca, Guaduas Guaduala Fms.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Moreno et al., 2013; Nie et al., 2012; Saylor et al., 2012; Caballero et al., 2013; Mora et al., 2010; Bayona et al., 2020
			Southern MMV	Paleocene local uplift and erosion of the CC provided Sandstones and conglomerates to the southern MMV	Cimarrona, Hoyon Fms.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2003
			MMV, western EC	Paleocene shift from craton to more proximal sources of sediment in the MMV and western EC	Lisama Fm.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Bayona et al., 2008, 2020; Moreno et al., 2011; Nie et al., 2012; Saylor et al., 2012; Caballero et al., 2013; Mora et al., 2010
			MMV, EC	A broad zone of deformation during the Paleocene allowed sediment contribution from local hills in the MMB and western EC	Lisama, Guaduas Fm.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Bayona et al., 2008, 2020; Parra et al., 2012;
			CeB, RB	The Paleocene erosion of the SNSM fed a fluvial-estuarine system that mixed with shallow marine sediments	Cuervos, Cerrejon Fm.	Strat, Prov.	Escalona and Mann, 2011; Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
			UMV	The high subsidence regime during the Paleocene allowed deposition of a thick mudstone succession in the UMV	Guaduala Fm.	Strat.	Ramon and Rosero, 2006
Early-middle Eocene	Farallon plate: Lateral change between continental and intraoceanic subduction. Initial arching of the trench geometry at the CSP triple junction	Arc	Western CC and RC	Early Eocene Farallon arc-related magmatism	In northern Colombia: Acandí, Mandé Batholith; In southern Colombia: Timbiquí Complex; in Ecuador: Silante and Macuchí arcs	Geoch, ADat.	Bayona et al., 2012; Cardona et al., 2014, 2018; Bustamante et al., 2017; Jaramillo et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019; Barbosa-Espitia et al., 2019
			Northern CC, SNSM	Early Eocene Caribbean arc-related magmatism	Hatillo, Sonsón, Santa Barbara Stock	Geoch, ADat.	Bayona et al., 2012; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019
		CC and western MV	Unroofing of 3–4 km of sedimentary section in the arc and proximal retroarc during the early Eocene		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2003	
	Caribbean plate: Highly oblique subduction	Forearc	TB, southern WC	Continued Late Cretaceous-Eocene unconformity in the forearc position		Strat, Prov.	Pardo-Trujillo et al., 2020
			SJR	During the middle Eocene, the San Jacinto accretionary wedge started to obduct west of the Romeral fault. Lower to middle Eocene unconformity		Strat, Prov.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2017; Kellogg et al., 2005; Escalona and Mann, 2011;

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
		Backarc	CB, western MB	The lower Eocene units were accumulated in continental fluvial environments in the Cesar and western Maracaibo basins	Cuervos and Marcelina Fms.	Strat, prov, Thch.	Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012
			CeB, RB, CB and MB	Onset of activity of the Cerrejon fault by the middle Eocene. Initial contribution from the Perijá Range and the Santander massif.	Mirador, La Loma, Tabaco and Misoa Fms.	Strat, prov, Thch.	Montes et al., 2010; Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012
			UMV	Early Eocene major folding and faulting along the western margin of the Girardot subbasin		Strat, seism.	Ramon and Rosero, 2006
			MMV	Late Eocene sourcing of sediments to the MMV from the La Cira-Infantas paleohigh	La Paz Fm.	Strat, prov, Thch.	Moreno et al., 2011; Nie et al., 2012; Saylor et al., 2012; Caballero et al., 2013; Mora et al., 2015
			EC	Initial cooling and uplift of the Guaduas syncline during middle Eocene	San Juan de Rio Seco Fm	Strat, Thch.	Parra et al., 2009
Middle Eocene - Oligocene	Farallon plate: Continued arching of the trench geometry at the CSP triple junction. Progressive slab flatenning;	Arc	CC	Magmatic quiescence in the arc during the late Eocene-Oligocene		ADat.	Villagómez et al., 2011; Bayona et al., 2012; Bustamante et al., 2017; Jaramillo et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019
			CC	The Romeral Fault System and the northern Palestina Fault System became inactive during the middle Eocene		Strat, Seism.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2017

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
	Caribbean plate: Change in convergence obliquity against South America. Slab breakoff by the late Eocene followed by slab flatening		CC	Decrease in relief of the CC after the middle Eocene. Moderate exhumation rate (<0.3 km/my)		Strat, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2003; Villagómez & Spikings, 2013; Zapata et al., 2021; León et al., 2021
			WCE, ECE	In Ecuador <1 km/my exhumation in the arc position during late Eocene - Oligocene was accompanied by coarse-grained sediments in the foreland	Upper Tiyuyacu Fm.	Strat, Thch.	Spikings et al., 2001; Villagómez & Spikings, 2013;
		Forearc	CUV	Reinitiation of sedimentation during the Oligocene in the CUV. Low energy meandering fluvial systems.	Amaga Fm.	Strat, Prov.	Silva-Tamayo et al., 2008; Lara et al., 2018; Zapata et al., 2021
			TB	Fine-grained clastic successions were accumulated in shelf and prodelta environments in the TB during the late Eocene-early Miocene	Lutitas de Remolino Grande Fm.	Strat, Prov.	Pardo-Trujillo et al., 2020
			SJR	Fore-arc extension, subsidence, and sedimentation of shallow marine deposits during the late Eocene-Oligocene. Advance of marine sedimentation from NW to SE	Chengue and San Jacinto Fms.	Strat, Prov, Seism.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2017

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
		Backarc	CC, EC, MMV	The middle-late Eocene was a time of decreased tectonic activity in the backarc position. Low accumulation rates.	Upper Mirador and Lower Esmeraldas Fms.	Strat, Prov, Thch.	Mora et al., 2013, 2020; Silva et al., 2013; Reyes-Harker et al., 2015
			MB	Eocene-Oligocene draining of the protoMagdalena River toward the Maracaibo Basin		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Ayala-Calvo et al., 2012; Caballero et al., 2013; Silva et al., 2013
			MMV	The Paleocene deformation front in the MMV was abandoned after the Eocene		Strat, Thch, palther	Parra et al., 2012; Sanchez et al., 2012; Caballero et al., 2013a
			EC	The deformation front migrated to the EC during the early Oligocene. Onset of inversion of former rift faults and rapid subsidence of the Llanos Foreland Basin.	C8 Fm.	Strat, Thch, palther	Mora et al., 2020; Parra et al., 2009; Mora et al., 2013a and Reyes-Harker et al., 2015
			SP, SM, EC	Regional uplift in the backarc position (SP, SM, EC) was ubiquitous during the Oligocene		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2005; Parra et al., 2009; Mora et al., 2013a; Caballero et al. 2013a, 2020; van der Lelij et al. 2016; Siravo et al., 2019; Horton et al., 2015
			Eastern flank of the EC	Growth strata and development of detachment folds in the Llanos foothills point to a first phase of deformation during the late Oligocene		Strat, Seism.	Martínez et al., 2022; Ortiz et al., 2022

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
			UMV	An Oligocene event of deformation in the UMV started the activity in the San Jacinto Fault and the growth of the San Francisco and La Hocha Anticlines		Strat, Seism.	Jiménez et al., 2012; Rosero et al., 2022
			GM	Deposition of Eocene–Oligocene strata in nonconformable contact upon basement of the GM	Pepino, Orteguzza Fms.	Strat, Seism.	Anderson et al., 2016; Wolaver et al., 2015
			PCA	Onset of counterclockwise vertical-axis rotation of blocks of the PCA during the Oligocene		Strat. Pmagn.	Montes et al., 2012
Late Oligocene - middle Miocene	Farallon/Nazca plate: Farallon breakup and steepening of subducting slab segments. Changing spreading center position and convergence obliquity. Further plate fragmentation.	Arc	CC	Renewed arc magmatism in the northern Andes during late Oligocene - early Miocene time	Cuembi, El Vergel, La Toma stocks, Piedrancha batholith	Geoch, ADat.	Wagner et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019; Marín-Cerón et al., 2019; Weber et al., 2020
			Panama	Renewed arc magmatism in the PCA during the late Oligocene	Mamonith batholith, volcanic units within the Las Cascadas, Cucaracha, Pedro Miguel Fms.	Geoch, ADat.	Lissinna, 2005; Farris et al., 2011; Wegner et al., 2011; Montes et al., 2012; Rooney et al., 2015
		Forearc	LMV	The change from deltaic to deep-marine deposits indicates that the proto-Magdalena river started supplying sediment from the ESE by the early Miocene	Upper Cienaga de Oro and Lower Porquero Fms.	Strat, Prov, Seism.	Reyes-Santos et al., 2000; Bernal-Olaya et al., 2015; Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2018

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
	Caribbean plate: Ongoing flat-slab subduction. Initial collision of the PCA against the continent. Lateral variation between subduction accretion (north), and subduction erosion (south).		LMV	The main extensional fault families in the LMV gradually decreased their activity during the Miocene		Strat, Seism.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2018
			TB, southern WC	Generalized exhumation in the Gorgona Island, the Tumaco Basin, and the southern part of the Western Cordillera during the early Miocene		Strat, Thch.	Barbosa–Espitia et al., 2013; Pardo-Trujillo et al., 2020
		Backarc	EC-Merida	The Bocono fault, and associated thrust faults started activity in late Oligocene to early Miocene times		Strat, Seism.	Parnaud et al., 1995; Montes et al., 2012
			EC	Moderate tectonic activity and exhumation in the EC during the early Miocene, however, paleo-elevations were below 1 km		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Parra et al., 2009; Mora et al., 2020
			UMV	An angular unconformity evidences a early Miocene deformation event that affected the Neiva subbasin and the east margin of the Girardot subbasin		Strat, Seism.	Ramon and Rosero, 2006
			Southern MMV	The development of lacustrine environments in the southern MMV evidences the cessation of deformation of the Villeta anticlinorium in middle Miocene time	Santa Teresa Fm.	Strat, Thch.	Gómez et al., 2003

Table S1 (continued)

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
			SNSM	During the Miocene, the Santa Marta fault caused a NE tilting of the Santa Marta Range		Strat, Thch.	Piraquive et al. 2018; Siravo et al., 2019
Late Miocene - Recent	<p>Nazca plate: The Coiba and Malpelo microplates were attached to the Nazca plate leading to more orthogonal convergence against South America. Continued arching of the trench geometry at the CSP triple junction. Renewed slab flattening behind the triple junction. Slab tearing during the Pliocene at 5.5°N.</p>	Arc	CC	Continued arc magmatism in the northern Andes during the middle Miocene to recent.	e.g. Combia Fm., Farallones batholith, Buritica, El Cerro, Paramo de Frontino, Quinchia, Tamesis, La Aurora porfiritic suites.	Geoch, ADat.	Wagner et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019; Marín-Cerón et al., 2019; Weber et al., 2020
			EC	North of 5.5°N, eastward migration of magmatism from the CC to the EC during the late Miocene	Paipa volcano	Geoch, ADat.	Pardo et al., 2005; Bernet et al., 2016; Wagner et al., 2017; Leal-Mejía et al., 2019; Marín-Cerón et al., 2019
			Panama	Quaternary adakitic volcanism in Panama		Geoch, ADat.	Lissinna, 2005; Farris et al., 2011; Wegner et al., 2011; Montes et al., 2012; Rooney et al., 2015
		Forearc	LMV	Gradual advance of the proto-Magdalena river which filled the Plato depocenter and reached the present-day coastline in early Pliocene times		Strat, Seism.	Mora_Bohórquez et al., 2018

Period	Generalized subduction setting	Domain	Location/Region	Tectonostratigraphic event	Units	Generic methods	Sources
	Caribbean plate: Slab breakoff in the suture between the PCA and South America. Continued flat-slab subduction. Slab tearing in the leading eastern edge of the slab.		SJFB	Unconformities in the sedimentary sequence indicate the last episode of uplifting of the SJFB between the Pliocene and Pleistocene		Strat, Seism.	Mora-Bohórquez et al., 2018
			CV	Mio-Pliocene coarsening -up sedimentary successions in the CV indicates topographic growth of the northern CC		Strat, Thch.	Lara et al., 2018; Zapata et al., 2021
		Backarc	SM	The SM underwent continuous uplifting on both sides of the Bucaramanga fault during the late Miocene-Pliocene, with more important vertical displacement of the eastern block		Strat, Prov, Thch.	Villamizar-Escalante 2017; Siravo et al., 2019
			EC	Estimated shortening rates show a dramatic increase at about 10 Ma, with gradual acceleration through the late Miocene, with values around 8 mm/yr during the Plio-Pleistocene.		Strat, Prov, Seism, Thch.	Mora et al., 2013; Parra et al., 2009; Reyes-Harker et al., 2015
			GM	Continued fault activity accommodated most of the uplift and exhumation of the Garzón Massif between the Late Miocene and Pliocene (3-6 Ma)		Strat, Prov, Seism, Thch.	Anderson et al., 2016; Saeid et al., 2017; Mora et al., 2020

Table S1 (continued). CC: Central Cordillera, EC: Eastern Cordillera, ECE: Eastern Cordillera of Ecuador, WC: Western Cordillera, WCE: Western Cordillera of Ecuador, RC: Real Cordillera, MV: Magdalena Valley, LMV: lower Magdalena Valley, MMV: middle Magdalena Valley, UMV: upper Magdalena Valley, SM: Santander massif, SNSM: Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, GM: Garzon massif, CV: Cauca valley, CUV: Cauca-Urrao valley, CB: Catatumbo basin, CeB: Cesar basin, MB: Maracaibo basin, RB: Rancheria basin, SP: Sierra de Perijá, SR: San Jacinto range, TB: Tumaco basin. Strat: Stratigraphy and cross cutting relationships, Seism: Seismic interpretation, Thch: Thermochronology, Prov: Provenance analysis, Geoch: Geochemistry, Adat: Absolute age dating, Pmagn: Paleomagnetism

Fig S1. Animated three-dimensional view of the present-day subducting Nazca/Coiba/Malpelo and Caribbean slabs beneath NWSA as interpreted from our tectonic reconstruction. The Tomographic model by Sun et al. (2022) supports the interpretation (the tomographic sections are orthogonally projected in depth). The interpretation of the model was made in the software MOVE.

(GIF)

Fig. S2. Proposed geometrical evolution of the Farallon, Nazca, Cocos, Malpelo, Coiba and Caribbean subduction beneath northwestern South America and eastern Central America in three-dimensional view. See the detailed description of this evolution in the manuscript.

Structural contours
 — Caribbean Plate
 — Farallon/Nazca Plate
 — Cocos Plate
 Contour interval: 20 km

▲ Restored magmatism
 ▲ Plate-motion direction (relative to South America)
 --- Abandoned Spreading center
 - - - Tear fault
 - - - Trench
 - - - Plate boundary

Fig S3. a-h) Alternative reconstruction of the South and Central American subduction zones considering that the Caribbean slab is hypothetically subducting east of the PCA (Our preferred reconstruction is included in the main body of the manuscript). Isolines correspond to subducting contours of the Farallon/Nazca/Coiba/Malpelo (green), Cocos (orange) and Caribbean (blue) slabs. i) Present-day structural map of the Nazca and Caribbean slabs beneath the northwestern corner of South America (Contour interval 25 km). White contours indicate age of entrance in the trench. Note that the subducting ages are not interpreted for the Caribbean slab east of the PCA. This is because this interpretation requires the continuous entry of new slab into the subduction zone after initial arc collision, which cannot be explain with the proposed kinematic model. Another shortcoming of this interpretation is that it cannot account for the prolific arc-related magmatism north of 5.5°N during the Miocene (f,g,h), since, according to this interpretation, that magmatism developed above a shallow Caribbean slab that subducted at a depth of less than 50 km.

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